

**Workshop on Artificial Intelligence Techniques for the Optimization of
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**Metaheuristic optimization for complex problems in the energy
domain**

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Abstract:

Power energy systems are evolving fast, adopting smart grid technologies, distributed and renewable energy resources, and new market structures that transform the electrical grid in unprecedented ways. In fact, in this new paradigm, classical optimization tools are reaching their limits in solving more realistic scenarios, i.e., considering high dimensionality, nonlinear constraints, parameter uncertainty, or resource distributed nature. Thus, energy experts are now looking for new forms of management and operation of power systems [1].

In that pursuit, metaheuristic optimization, a computational intelligence search procedure to find good solutions to complex problems, is raising as an effective problem-solver achieving a good compromise between “optimal” and “practical” solutions [2], [3].

In this talk, we are going to motivate the use of metaheuristic optimization to handle complex problems in the energy domain. We will show some of the advantages that metaheuristics present over other mathematical approaches, e.g., their ability to solve problems with incomplete and imperfect information, limited computation capacity, or uncertainty of parameters. The talk will also include a rigorous critique of the limitations and issues that metaheuristics face. For instance, the ever-increasing set of nature-inspired (and not precisely novel) algorithms [2], the inability to provide optimality guarantees [3], and the lack of explanation of obtained solutions will be criticized aiming at overcoming such issues in the future.

We are also going to present some success histories and case studies on the application of metaheuristics in the energy domain [4], [5], to motivate further the usage of such alternative solvers in the field.

Related References:

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- [2] K. Sörensen, “Metaheuristics-the metaphor exposed,” *Int. Trans. Oper. Res.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 3–18, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1111/itor.12001.
- [3] B. Doerr and F. Neumann, *Theory of evolutionary computation: Recent developments in discrete optimization*. Springer Nature, 2019.
- [4] F. Lezama, J. Soares, Z. Vale, J. Rueda, S. Rivera, and I. Elrich, “2017 IEEE competition on modern heuristic optimizers for smart grid operation: Testbeds and results,” *Swarm Evol. Comput.*, vol. 44, pp. 420–427, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.swevo.2018.05.005.
- [5] F. Lezama *et al.*, “Bidding in local electricity markets with cascading wholesale market integration,” *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 131, p. 107045, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107045.